

Chemical Examination of *Mundulea Suberosa*. Part III. Isolation of Mundulone*

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Besides munetone, another isoflavone, m. p. 170-80°, has been isolated from the root bark of *Mundulea suberosa*, which has been found identical with mundulone, an isoflavone of novel complexity, obtained from the African variety of *M. sericea*.

Narayana and Rangaswami¹ reported the isolation of a crystalline substance, "Mundulca substance A", m. p. 180-82°, having a probable formula $C_{25}H_{24}O_6$ from the seeds of *Mundulea suberosa* in 0.15% yield. But no further work on the constitution was reported.

Recently Ollis and co-workers² have examined the bark of *Mundulea sericea* of South African origin. In view of the claim³ that the bark is used to repel crocodiles, the above investigators have made a detailed chromatographic separation of the bark extractive and have reported the isolation and characterisation of a number of crystalline compounds of novel complexity.

The isolation and characterisation of munetone (I), the principal extractive of the root bark of *Mundulea suberosa* obtained from the Western Ghats of Maharashtra State, have already been reported⁴. It will be seen that while no mention of munetone was reported by the English workers, the compounds characterised by the latter could not as yet be obtained from the Indian variety of *Mundulea suberosa*. In view of this and from the biogenetic relationship, it was of interest to reinvestigate the problem and as such a systematic chromatographic examination of the ether extractive of the root-bark of *Mundulea suberosa* was undertaken. In course of chromatographic separation, munetone was first isolated with benzene, after which the chromatogram was eluted with ether-chloroform and chloroform; the fractions were freed from the solvent and crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m. p. 179-80°, yield 0.35% on the weight of the dry root bark. The analysis corresponded to $C_{26}H_{26}O_6$. Like munetone⁴ this substance was also found to have an isoflavone constitution, since on alkaline hydrolysis it produced formic acid, characterised through the formaldehyde-chromotropic acid test and a deoxybenzoic acid, m. p. 160°, in about 95% yield, from which the original starting material was resynthesised with ethyl orthoformate-pyridine-piperidine according to the method of Sathe and Venkataraman⁵ in 65% yield. It was of interest to note that this synthesis could also be achieved without pyridine being used in the reaction mixture⁶. From all these characteristics the substance

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1. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 105.

2. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 150; 1960, 176, 177.

3. Chopra *et al.*, "Indigenous Drugs of India" Publ. by Dhur, Calcutta, 1958, p. 588.

4. Dutta, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 716; 1959, 36, 165.

5. *Curr. Sci.*, 1949, 18, 373.

6. Venkataraman and coworkers, unpublished work.

appeared to be similar to mundulone (II), isolated by Ollis *et al.*². A sample of the latter was made available by Prof. Ollis (to whom our grateful thanks are due) and both the compounds were found to be identical in all respects; there was no depression in the mixed m. p. and the IR and UV spectra were identical.

(I)
Munetone.

(II)
Mundulone.

EXPERIMENTAL

The dried and powdered root-bark of *mundulea suberosa* was extracted with ether at room temperature for several days. The solvent was removed and the resulting resinous material dried under vacuum according to the method already described⁴.

The resin (40 g.) was powdered and dissolved in dry pure benzene (200 ml) and passed over a column of alumina in benzene. It was followed by benzene, ether, chloroform, acetone, and ethanol, gradually increasing the proportion of the subsequent solvents. The different fractions were collected and examined separately.

From the benzene extract, munetone was obtained, which on recrystallisation from absolute ethanol melted at 192-93°, yield 1.2 g. (0.3% on the basis of the dry root-bark). Mixed melting point with an authentic sample of munetone was undepressed and the infrared spectra were identical.

From the ether-benzene (5:95 and 10:90) fraction, on removal of the solvent a solid material was obtained which on repeated crystallisation from ethanol furnished light yellow needles, m. p. 214-16°. Further work was not possible with this compound due to extremely poor yield of the substance. From the ether-chloroform (5:95 and 10:90) fractions, a compound was obtained which crystallised from ethanol as colorless fine needles, m. p. 179-80°, yield 1.4 g. (0.35% on the basis of the weight of the dry root-bark). It did not produce any coloration with ferric chloride solution. It is insoluble in petroleum ether, ether, hexane, cyclohexane, tetrahydrofuran, sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, dioxane, benzene, and fairly soluble in methanol, ethanol, and acetone. (Found on drying over P₂O₅ for 6 hours under vacuum: C, 71.6; H, 6.2. C₂₆H₂₆O₆ requires C, 71.98; H, 5.99%). The IR spectrum showed strong absorption bands at 3400, 1620, 1282, 1210, 1151, 1090, 1050, 994, 963, 837, 776cm⁻¹ (nujol); UV spectrum of the compound showed maxima at 244 mμ (ε 43,000) and 309 mμ (ε 17,200).

Alkaline Hydrolysis.—To the substance (1 g.), taken in a minimum amount of EtOH, was added 3% EtOH-KOH (40 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hours on a water bath. The solution was cooled and acidified with dilute phosphoric acid, when a precipitate was formed; it was filtered, washed with water, and dried; yield 902 mg.

The aqueous layer from the above reaction product was steam-distilled and the distillate tested for formic acid as follows. A few drops of the solution were mixed with a drop of 2*N*-HCl and magnesium powder was added till gas evolution ceased. A few crystals of chromotropic acid in H₂SO₄ (conc., 3 ml) was then added. The mixture was warmed on a water bath for 10 minutes, when a violet-pink colour appeared indicating the presence of formic acid. A blank test with distilled water and very dilute formic acid was made for comparison.

The above crude product, obtained by hydrolysis, was crystallised from methanol as colorless thick prism, m.p. 180°. It gave a deep violet colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found on drying over P₂O₅: C, 71.06; H, 6.9. C₂₅H₂₈O₆ requires C, 70.76; H, 6.60%).

This product obviously has a carbon atom less than the parent compound—this indication coupled with the identification of formic acid in the hydrolytic products gave the clue to the parent compound to have an isoflavone structure. The above inference was confirmed by resynthesising the parent compound from the hydrolysed material.

A mixture of the compound (205 mg), ethyl orthoformate (1 ml), dry piperidine (0.05 ml), and pyridine (6 ml) was refluxed at 140° for 9 hours. After cooling, water was added to the reaction mixture and acidified with HCl (dil.). The light brown precipitate was collected, washed with water, and dried; yield 140 mg. (35%). It was taken in benzene, chromatographed over alumina, and eluted with benzene. On removal of the solvent, the product crystallised from methanol as colorless prism, m. p. 179-80°. The mixed melting point with the parent compound was undepressed and the IR spectra were identical.

In a separate experiment, it was observed that pyridine was not essential in the above reaction and better yield (70%) was obtained when the same reaction was conducted without the addition of pyridine.

Attempts were made to prepare a 2-methylisoflavone compound from the hydrolytic product in the usual way with anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, but a low-melting substance was obtained which could not be crystallised.

By courtesy of Prof. Ollis of the Bristol University a sample of mundulone was obtained and a comparison was made with the substance, m. p. 179-80°, isolated above. It was found that both the substances were identical in all respects since there was no depression in the mixed melting point and the IR and UV spectra were identical.

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